

HIGH-POWER MEDIUM-VOLTAGE SUPERCONDUCTING CABLES FOR EUROPE’S ENERGY TRANSITION

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Abstract

Superconducting cables have been proven in multiple tests and utility installations, which highlighted their compact size, low energy losses, and reliability. This can make the technology economically attractive for many applications. A particularly interesting case is the DC high-power transfer at medium voltage (MVDC). The high current capability of the superconductor allows for a reduction in voltage while maintaining or increasing the power transfer level. A main motivation for the development of MVDC superconducting export cables is that costly and complex high-voltage converter stations can be eliminated when going from high- to medium-voltage, allowing for significant overall cost reductions. This is very relevant for offshore applications. The European project SCARLET develops and demonstrates MVDC cables at the gigawatt level, including their protection requirements. Some of the SCARLET highlights are offshore superconducting cables, the combined hydrogen and electricity transmission in the same pipeline, and the demonstration of a 10 kADC fault current limiter module. This paper describes the superconducting MVDC cable concepts and the main challenges needed to develop and type test the cables.

1 Introduction

In recent years, superconducting cables have reached performance levels positioning them on the threshold for commercial utilization. At the same time, the ongoing energy transition is creating a new paradigm and leading to new requirements. For instance, power generation in remote areas requires efficient power export, and liquid hydrogen (LH₂) pipeline systems are foreseen, which could be combined with electricity transmission. This is where superconducting cables have the potential to contribute in a cost-effective way.

More than 20 pilots of high-temperature superconducting (HTS) cables, both DC and AC, have been installed and tested around the world since 2000. These pilots aimed to validate the feasibility of the manufacturing, as well as the performance and reliability of the cables and their accessories (terminations, joints, thermal shrinkage compensation) for various use cases. These projects have convincingly passed all the demonstration steps proving that HTS systems of a few kilometres are feasible and can be commercialized for a very wide range of parameters. Some of the most prominent examples [1] are listed in Table 1 and are briefly described in the following.

A district of Essen, Germany was energized for more than

Table 1: Examples of existing and planned HTS projects and their objectives, adapted from [1]

Projects (and status)	Providing N-1 redundancy	Increased power density	Increasing renewable integration
ComEd AC cable (energized)	👍	👍	
Ampacity AC cable (deenergized)	👍	👍	
KEPCO AC Munsan cable (planned)	👍	👍	
NEDO AC cable (deenergized)		👍	
Shanghai AC cable (energized)	👍	👍	
Ishikari DC cable		👍	👍
SuperRail DC cable (planned)		👍	
SCARLET DC cable (planned)		👍	👍

seven years without any interruption or reported problems using a kilometre-long AC superconducting cable at 10 kV and 40 MVA in the AmpaCity project [2]. The COMED project in

Chicago aims at increasing the resilience of the business district by connecting three substations with a 12 kV / 62 MVA link [3]. In Japan, the world’s first demonstration of a tri-axial superconducting cable system installed in a commercial chemical plant took place in 2020 [1]. Also in Asia, a 1.2 km long HTS cable at 35 kV / 2.2 kA has been operating in Shanghai since 2021. In Korea, KEPCO plans to install two kilometre-long cables at 23 kV / 60 MVA to connect the Munsan and Seonyu substations. [1] Also in planning is the SuperLink project in Munich (110 kV, 500 MVA, 12 km) [4].

For DC operation, a first superconducting cable (20 kV, 5 kA, 500 m) was tested in 2020 at Ishikari site in Japan, followed by a second cable (20 kV, 2.5 kA, 1000 m) that is still ongoing. These bipolar coaxial cables connected a data centre and a solar farm [5]. In Europe, the SuperRail cable project (1.5 kV, 3.5 kA, 80 m) at the Montparnasse railway station in Paris [6] will be energized in 2025, increasing the power transfer in existing ducts and avoiding costly creation of new rights of way.

All the projects mentioned so far are carried out with ReBCO or BSCCO tapes operating at 70 K in liquid nitrogen. For MgB₂-based cables operating below 25 K, the most important project was the EU-funded Best Paths, validating high-voltage DC (HVDC) superconducting links in the first demonstration of a 3-gigawatt-class superconducting cable system operating at 320 kV and 10 kA [7]. Recently, the IRIS project has started in Italy with the aim of providing a cable test facility for 50 kV and 40 kA [8]. To achieve a temperature below 25 K, the use of LH₂ is a promising alternative to the helium gas used so far. The combination of hydrogen transport and a superconducting cable was proposed twenty years ago [9] and demonstrated in 2013 in a proof-of-concept MgB₂-based cable [10].

To complete the picture of possible applications of superconducting power cables, we present here the development of MVDC superconducting cable systems carried out in the framework of the European project SCARLET.

2 The SCARLET project

SCARLET (Superconducting cables for sustainable energy transition) includes 14 partners and is driven by the idea of utilizing the high current capability of superconducting cables to go from HVDC to MVDC keeping the same level of transmitted power [11, 12]. The objective is to develop and industrially manufacture superconducting cable systems at the gigawatt level, bringing them to the last qualification step before commercialization.

The project started in September 2022 and has a duration of four and a half years. The main working areas are illustrated in Fig. 1. Onshore HTS and MgB₂ cables are developed and demonstrated, whereas reinforced cryostats will be developed

Fig. 1: Superconducting cables investigated in SCARLET. This figure has been reproduced with permission from IEEE, 2023.

and tested for offshore cables. The system protection activities include the demonstration of a resistive superconducting fault current limiter (RSFCL) module to protect the switch gear.

In addition to the demonstrators, system architectures are investigated and designed to utilize the capabilities of the cables, and techno-economic studies will be carried out.

2.1. HTS cables

In SCARLET, studies are performed for onshore and offshore HTS MVDC cable systems to develop and optimize the components required for the large-scale deployment of these technologies.

As shown in Fig. 2, several cable designs are considered at 10 kA and 50 or 100 kVDC depending on the final user requirements (1 or 2 GW) and other constraints such as redundancy: two monopoles with or without HTS screen and a bipolar cable with a separate cryogenic return line.

For these designs, the behaviour of the MVDC cable system during specific transient electrical phenomena has been simulated showing a good tolerance to the fault current, with only 1 K temperature increase after two peaks of 40 kA within 4 s. Also, multi-kilometric systems require very efficient cable cryostats to maintain the low temperature along the entire cable at a minimal cost. A dedicated study is ongoing, simultaneously with the creation of an IEC working group to standardise the measurements and give a strong basis for reducing the thermal losses of the flexible cryostats surrounding the superconducting cable core and the cryogenic fluid.

Fig. 2: MVDC power link at 1 GW based on two monopolar HTS cables carrying 10 kA each at +50 kV and -50 kV without (a) and with (b) an HTS screen, with LN₂ circulation in one pole and return in the other; (c) MVDC power link at 1 GW comprising one HTS cable with two symmetric concentric poles at +50 kV and - 50 kV carrying 10 kA, with the LN₂ return in a separate line. This figure has been reproduced with permission from IEEE, 2023.

For onshore solutions, MVDC networks have already been studied to bring power in the city centres thanks to recent development of power electronics at 54 kVDC [13]. The unique properties of the HTS circuits can bring more flexibility or even enable to connect large power substations in the suburbs to the centres thanks to very narrow cable routes or reuse of existing rights of ways with no thermal or electromagnetic impact. Hence, the focus of the onshore solutions will be on standard and modular designs for cables and accessories, which would ease the deployment of multi-kilometre systems. Especially the cooling system is still a critical component for the deployment of long-length HTS systems, and an optimization study dedicated to their reliability, maintenance, footprint, and integration into modular HTS cable systems, will be performed.

Most of the technology bricks available from onshore superconducting cable system applications are directly

transferable to submarine applications. Indeed, technologies developed for terminations, cooling systems, core of the superconducting cable immersed in LN₂, and related manufacturing processes are not really impacted by submarine constraints and remain mainly unchanged. Some preliminary studies emphasize that one of the main technical challenges for subsea applications is the adaptation of the cryogenic envelopes surrounding the superconducting cables and containing the pressurized LN₂ [14]. In maritime environments, these cryogenic envelopes must withstand the outer water pressure and various dynamic mechanical loads which could be functional, environmental, or even accidental.

Another challenge is the management of the cooling technology over very long offshore distances with the need for intermediate platforms. Our first thermal and hydraulic studies indicate that the cable systems shown in Fig. 2 can be cooled on one side with one cooling station for lengths of 20 to nearly 40 km, with the distance depending strongly on the sea depth and the choice of cable cryostat.

2.2 MgB₂-based MVDC superconducting cable for hybrid power distribution

In addition to the work on HTS cables, SCARLET will develop LH₂-cooled MVDC cables based on the MgB₂ superconductor following a very similar technical approach as described in the previous section.

As an energy storage medium, hydrogen has a key and global role in achieving the decarbonization goals, while also providing independence and security of energy supply. An efficient solution for distributing large quantities of hydrogen is to use its liquid phase at a temperature of around 20 K and atmospheric pressure.

Inserting a very compact superconducting cable in an LH₂ pipeline offers a unique solution to simultaneously transmit the two energy vectors electricity and hydrogen, so-called hybrid or dual transmission. Hybrid transmission opens various business opportunities based on the placement of such a system in the power grids and hydrogen pipeline networks. This is especially appealing for transportation systems and energy-intensive industries, where large quantities of both electrical energy and hydrogen are needed. Some relevant examples are highlighted in Table 2.

At the LH₂ temperature of 20 K, commercial superconducting materials such as HTS and MgB₂ are very efficient. In addition, using MgB₂ results in very compact MVDC cables that can be inserted in the LH₂ pipeline with only a marginal decrease in the hydrogen mass flow. The free section for LH₂ circulation can be easily adjusted to the needs of the end user. Such a hybrid system transforms the cost of the coolant needed for the superconducting cable into a source of profit by charging for the hydrogen delivery. Sharing the same

transmission infrastructure for electricity and hydrogen also reduces investment costs.

Table 2: Opportunities for hybrid power distribution

	Hydrogen needs	Electricity needs
	10 t/h in steel smelter for reduction reaction	50 to 200 MW
	15 t on board; for 2-5 ships approx. 2-3 t/h	50-200 MW per ship and port infrastructure
	150 to 200 kg on board; for 20 trains 3t/d	10 MW per substation and railway station infrastructure
	80 kg/truck; for 100 trucks 0.3 t/h	100-200 kW per fast charge station; for 100 vehicles 20 MW
	up to 9 t per aircraft; for line airplane 10-30 t/h	Large range for electric aircraft 50 kW to 1 MW and airport infrastructure

To demonstrate the readiness of such dual-transport systems, SCARLET will develop a 500 MW DC monopolar cable system (1 GW in bipolar design) transferring 20 kA at 25 kV [15]. As illustrated in Fig. 3, the proposed diameter of the insulated cable is 24 mm including the 25 kV-class insulation. The cable size is well suited for pipelines with an LH₂ transport capacity of 2-10 t/h, which is identified as appropriate for ports and industrial demand.

Apart from demonstrating the feasibility and maturity of all the key components of such a superconducting cable, the system will be tested under the strictest consideration of all the safety requirements for operation in LH₂. Type testing will be followed by operation in the field for a 6-month period at the very end of the project.

Fig. 3: Typical cross section of a hybrid energy system consisting of 2 x 500 MW MVDC cables and LH₂ distribution of up to 10 t/h, as proposed in SCARLET.

2.3. System architecture and protection

The use of MVDC superconducting cables, rather than HVDC resistive cables, for the export of remote offshore wind power can highly simplify the offshore conversion scheme and shrink the size of the necessary offshore platform by at least 50%. In particular, SCARLET proposes the windmill output voltage to be directly set to the MVDC transport voltage, suppressing the need for an offshore AC to DC conversion station (see Fig. 4). This can be done with little effort, as windmill towers already incorporate a conversion chain that can be modified to achieve the proper DC output voltage.

Fig. 4: Illustration of the opportunity to suppress the offshore conversion station by using an MVDC superconducting cable for offshore wind power export. This figure has been reproduced with permission from IEEE, 2023.

On the onshore side, the MVDC conversion station architecture needs to be redesigned compared to the HVDC case. State-of-the-art converters are of the modular multilevel type using power electronic switches limited to 2 – 3 kA nominal current. To manage nominal currents of 10 kA and more, SCARLET proposes a parallel scheme of converters, where each branch can be individually isolated by a DC circuit breaker in case of a converter fault. This allows for the continuity of service at reduced power after the isolation of the faulty branch. This converter structure can also be applied for other use cases such as the interconnection of power systems or the power supply to very high loads like industrial sites or ports.

Contrary to resistive cables, the heating of a superconducting cable should be avoided in case of a fault. Indeed, this results in the boiling of its cooling fluid, inducing a long recovery time of its operating conditions. To prevent this, the combination of a converter side DC breaker and a resistive superconducting fault current limiter (RSFCL) is very efficient. SCARLET proposes to model different MVDC electrical systems of the GW level, integrating the electro-

thermal models of the cables as well as RSFCL and DC circuit breakers to evaluate the benefit of this protection scheme [16].

As highlighted in Fig. 5, the demonstration of an RSFCL with 10 kADC nominal current is ongoing, through the HTS tape characterisation and the design, production and testing of several modules as well as dedicated high-voltage cryogenic current leads.

Fig. 5: RSFCL in the high-power test facility of SuperGrid Institute.

3 Conclusion

Two types of MVDC superconducting cables are developed and tested in SCARLET: one based on HTS tapes and one on MgB₂ wires. The developed cables are studied for multiple uses, including offshore applications and combined electricity and LH₂ transport. To maximize the overall benefits of the cables, the system architecture is thoroughly investigated, and a protection scheme is developed, including a resistive superconducting fault current limiter. The SCARLET activities will contribute to the work of including MVDC superconducting cables in the standardization framework, for instance by proposing type test recommendations for these cables.

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